

QUANTIFICATION OF ENZYMES AND HISTOLOGY CHANGES BELONGS TO THE PINK BOLL WORM *PECTINOPHORA GOSSYPIELLA* (SAUNDERS) (LEPIDOPTERA: GELECHIIDAE) EXPOSED TO SOME INSECTICIDE TOXICITIES

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ABSTRACT. The direct effects of insecticide class toxicities on many numbers of insect body enzymes, is the strong asset to measure the biological effects. Then much quantity of *P.gossypiella* larvae collected from several fields were treated with sublethal concentration equal LC₅₀ values of some recommended insecticides two of organophosphates and pyrethroids in addition to orange oil were selected and evaluated about most enzymes specific detoxification mechanisms exist and its mid gut histological changes of effected bodies were investigated. Data of enzyme investigations shows that cypermethrin was recorded high value of *AChE* activity was 305 (ug AchBr/min/g.b.wt), followed by malathion was 268 then profenofos was 243 and lambdacyhalothrin was 217.3. Nevertheless, orange oil was recorded high value in GST activity monitoring followed by cypermethrin, malathion then profenofos. Moreover, orange oil recorded the least value of alkaline phosphatase, alpha, beta esterases activity and the total protein. The highest values were cypermethrin in alkaline phosphatase, profenofos in alpha and beta esterase and the total protein. The percentage of inhibition of Enzymes activity compared with the control were calculated. Histological observations in all slides were in larvae mid-gut were detected the differences between insecticide toxicities.

Keywords: *Enzymes, acetylcholinesterase, alpha esterase, beta esterase, alkaline phosphatase, histology, Pectinophora gossypiella, insecticides.*

INTRODUCTION

The biological functions of pesticides and drugs exposure of any organism is the direct effects to be measure on many numbers of enzymes, that are large proteins constructed from different amino acids which empower specific chemical reactions to occur concluding some biochemical processes [1]. Insecticides are the essential key concepts to control many pests in farming to prevent crop damage than other practices. Insecticide resistance is a serious worldwide problem, defined as the decline limits of the ability of insecticides to control pests [2]. Thus, we can measure the biological effects of pesticide exposure other than toxicity effect to introduce subsidized insecticide resistance management by valuable information about how insecticide can affect a pest species under control and define its mode of actions. Many classes of insecticides affect insect body enzymes such as Organophosphate (OP) and Pyrethroids (Py) that act on acetylcholinesterase (*AChE*), leading to development of cholinergic toxicity, over enzymatic activity decreases [3]. While pyrethroids act on the sodium channels in the nerve membrane (neurotoxic) and do not have carcinogenic, mutagenic and teratogenic effects. [4] cited about the importance of measuring insect enzymes activities toward insecticide toxicities and applications. Since the 1990s, insecticides

acting at the nicotinic acetylcholine receptor considered the target of commercially insecticide products that have been widely used because their high efficacy against a wide range of important insect pests as lepidopteran, coleopteran and hemipteran insects [5]. The glutathione S-transferase (GST) is one of the intracellular enzymes involved in the detoxification of endogenous and xenobiotic compounds via glutathione conjugation, [6]. A phosphatase enzyme is essential to many biological functions, it uses water to cleave a phosphoric acid monoester into a phosphate ion and an alcohol in process called hydrolases and remove phosphate groups from molecules [7]. The Egyptian cotton crop suffer seasonally infestation by a such arthropod group of bollworms complex one of them is *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). Pink bollworm larvae fed on buds, causing fruit shedding, seed loss and moths represent a commercial problem because its larval stage frequently enters diapause while in seed capsules, emerging after long lived for about than 50 days at different climate conditions and survived for many months [8, 9]. Insecticide application in sequential can control only the eggs and first instars remain outside bolls because larval stage enters bolls and remain inside until pupal emergence. In addition to the repeated insecticide application may cause a development of metabolic resistance toward most classes of insecticides represent biochemical mechanisms and difficult problem fronting the effective control [10, 11]. For mitigating insecticide resistance crisis, the most applicable idea is the chemical compound replacements through uses another insecticide have other mode of action. But the other promising ideas are uses plant extract or essential Oils and their constituents are considered one of pesticide alternatives uses to control pests [12].

In this study, *P.gossypiella* larvae collected from several fields were treated with some recommended insecticides two of (OP and Py), in addition to orange oil the commercial product extracted from orange peels [13] (*Citrus sinensis*) (L.) Osbeck (PREV-AM®) have variety of pest control success were chosen and evaluated about most enzymes specific detoxification were exist and its larvae mid gut histological changes of affected larvae bodies were investigated.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Insect sources and Insecticides

Big bulk of cotton plant bolls collected from Menufia governorate cotton cultivated field heavily infested with *P. gossypiella* larvae (Saunders), transferred to laboratory and the fourth instar larvae extracted from bolls and placed on petri dish provided with piece of cotton for maintenance used directly for bioassay and other bulk maintained for sublethal effect evaluation on some important detoxification enzymes. Information of insecticides tested in this study found in table (1).

Insect preparations and insecticide treatments

The bioassay procedure was completed using filter paper saturated with 5 ml of each concentration were applied of the insecticide formulations of four OP, Py and orange oil serial concentrations dissolved in acetone, placed on petri dish, and left to dry. Then each dish provided with ten larvae 3rd instar according to [14]. Control treated with acetone only. Four replicates were performed for each insecticide concentration and. Dishes maintained under laboratory conditions. Mortality counted after 24 hrs of treatments and data statistically analyzed using Polo software [15] for calculate LC₅₀, LC₉₀ and slope of toxicity line according to [16]. For sublethal concentration administration, more than 500 individual larvae were exposed to LC₅₀ of each

insecticide in separate container using the saturated filter paper technique and left to dry. Then the survived larvae from insecticides LC₅₀ treatment were collected and kept in deep freezer (-20 °C) till biochemical investigations.

Enzymes activity determinations

Insects tissue preparations for biochemical analysis

The insects were homogenized in distilled water (50 mg /1 ml), in a chilled glass Teflon tissue homogenizer (ST – 2 Mechanic-Preczyina, Poland). Homogenates were centrifuged at 8000 r.p.m. for 15 min at 5 °C in a refrigerated centrifuge. The deposits were discarded, and the supernatants were kept in a deep freezer at -20°C until use for biochemical assays. Double beam ultraviolet / visible spectrophotometer (Spectronic 1201, Milton Roy Co., USA) was used to measure absorbance of colored substances or metabolic compounds.

The following enzymes activities were determined

Determination of AchE

Activity measured according to [17], using acetylcholine bromide (*AchBr*) as substrate. The reaction mixture contained 200 µl enzyme solution, 0.5 ml 0.067 M phosphate buffer (pH7) and 0.5 ml *AchBr* (3 mM). The test tubes were incubated at 37 °C for exactly 30 min. 1 ml of alkaline hydroxylamine (equal volume of 2 M hydroxylamine chloride and 3.5 M NaOH) was added to the test tubes. Then 0.5 ml of HCl (1 part of conc. HCl and 2 parts of ΔH₂O) was added. The mixture was shaken vigorously and allowed to stand for 2 min. 0.5 ml of ferric chloride solution (0.9 M FeCl₃ in 0.1M HCl) was added and mixed well. The decrease in *AchBr* resulting from hydrolysis by *AchE* was read at 515 nm.

Determination of (GST)

Through catalyzing the conjugation of reduced glutathione (GSH) with 1-chloro 2, 4-dinitrobenzene (CDNB) via the -SH group of glutathione. The conjugate, S-(2,4-dinitro-phenyl)-L-glutathione could be detected as the method of [18]. The reaction mixture consisted of 1 ml of the potassium salt of phosphate buffer (pH6.5), 100µl of GSH and 200µl of larval homogenate. The reaction started by the addition of 25µl of the substrate CDNB solution. The concentration of both GSH and CDNB was adjusted to be 5mM and 1mM, respectively. Enzyme and reagents were incubated at 30°C for 5 min. The increment in absorbance at 340 nm was recorded to determine the nanomole substrate conjugated/min/larva using a molar extinction coefficient of 9.6/mM/cm.

Determination of alkaline phosphatases

Determined according to [19]. In this method, the phenol released by enzymatic hydrolysis of disodium phenylphosphate reacts with 4-aminoantipyrine, and potassium ferricyanide, then the brown color is produced. The reaction mixture consisted of 1 ml carbonate buffer (pH 10.4) for alkaline phosphatase, 1 ml of 0.01 M disodium phenylphosphate (substrate), and 0.1 ml sample. Mix and incubate for exactly 30 min at 37 C⁰. At the end of incubation period .0.8 ml of 0.5 N NaoH was added to stop the reaction. Then 1.2 ml of 0.5 N NaHCO₃, followed by 1 ml of 4-aminoantipyrine solution (1%) and 1 ml potassium ferricyanide (0.5 %) were added. The produced color was measured immediately at 510 nm. The enzyme activity is expressed by unit (U), where 1 unit will hydrolyze 1.0 u mole of p-nitophenyl phosphate per minute at 37 C⁰ and pH 10.4 and 4.8 for alkaline phosphatases.

Determination of α -esterases and β -esterases w

Determined according to [20] using α -naphthyl acetate or β -naphthyl acetate as substrates, respectively. The reaction mixture consisted of 5ml substrate solution (3×10^{-4} M α - or β -naphthylacetate, 1% acetone and 0.1M phosphate buffer, pH7) and 20 μ l of larval homogenate. The mixture was incubated for exactly 15 min at 27°C, then 1 ml of diazoblue color reagent (prepared by mixing 2 parts of 1% diazoblue B and 5 parts of 5% sodium lauryl sulphate) was added. The developed color was read at 600 or 555 nm. α - and β -naphthol standard curves were prepared by dissolving 20 mg α - or β -naphthol in 100ml phosphate buffer, pH7 (stock solution). Ten milliliters of stock solution were diluted up to 100ml by the buffer. Aliquots of 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.8 and 1.6 ml of diluted solution (equal to 2, 4, 8, 16 and 32 μ g naphthol) were pipetted into test tubes and completed to 5 ml by phosphate buffer. One milliliter of diazo blue reagent was added, and the developed color was red.

The total protein content

Total proteins were determined by the method of [21]. Protein reagent was prepared by dissolving 100mg of Coomassie Brilliant blue G-250 in 50ml 95% ethanol and 100ml 85% (W/V), of phosphoric acid were added and a final volume adjusted to 1 liter. Sample solution (50 μ l) or for preparation of standard curve 50 μ l of serial concentrations containing 10 to 100 μ g bovine serum albumin were pipetted into test tubes. The test tube volume was adjusted to 1 ml with phosphate buffer (0.1M, pH 6.6). Five millimeters of protein reagent were added, and the contents were mixed either by vortexing. The absorbance at 595 nm was measured after 2 min, and before 1 hr, against blank prepared from 1 ml of phosphate buffer and 5 ml protein reagent.

Sample preparations for the histological technique

A large quantity of *P. gossypiella* Larvae survived the sublethal treatment of each insecticide after 24 h of exposure were collected and the healthy ones were chosen to transfer to histology lab. The method of killing and fixing were applied. Some of the collected control and treated Larvae were fixed in 10% formalin solution. About ten larvae were moved in vials and kept in refrigerator till cutting. The fixed specimens were trimmed, washed, and dehydrated in ascending grades of alcohols, cleaned in xylene, embedded in paraffin then sectioned about (4-6 micron) cutting sections with a microtome in the mid gut. All slides were stained with hematoxylin-phloxine-eosin-saffron. Slides were examined with an optical microscope, and images were taken with a digital microscope camera, all procedures was according to [22].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Bioassay Toxicity results

Toxicity response results (Slop, intercept, LC₅₀, LC₉₀, and chi-squared) of the OP and Py insecticide treatments in contact bioassay against the pink bull worm *P. gossypiella* larvae collected from Menufia governorate were found in table (1). Lambdacyhalothrin is an effective insecticide followed by profenofos and cypermethrin but malathion was the least effective. In addition orange oil gave fine results of toxicity against this pest where LC₅₀ was 1.1 ppm prove reality of using as prominent insecticide for urgent IPM management. Generally, all insecticide tested showed moderate effect when focused on the low values of the ppm detected from this investigation. These results may be because the high susceptibility to insecticides and the

development of resistance status not profitable and maybe toxicity values was lowered than the past years of monitoring. Data does not need to compare with susceptible strain and requires evaluating some common enzymes to compare activities toward those insecticide exposures to insure the insecticide that have more inhibitory effect to enzymes activity under investigation. Some data that subsidize the efficiency of insecticide application differences, in field, trials, moderate reduction in bollworms at application of the sequences of biocides (Spinosad, Azadirachtin and *Bacillus thuringiensis*), IGRs and Py when sprayed three times alone or alternative with other three sprays at 15 days intervals. This data was attained by [11]. During the cotton seasons of 2009 in Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate, where infestation started with a small number of larvae in late July but increased gradually at the end of each season. Generally, in Egypt *P. gossypiella* is serious pest was easy to control by insecticide alone or in rotation and by other different control methods [9].

Table 1. Data of Op and Py, toxicity responses against *P. gossypiella* larvae analysis.

Pesticide	ai%	Trade	Slope	Intercept	LC ₅₀ (95 %	LC ₉₀ (95 %	χ^2
Profenofos	10%EC	Profile	1.63-	4.3	2.66(1.46-	16.3(8.9-	0.96
Malathion	57%EC	Chemnova	1.73-	3.34	8.9(5.1-	48.6(27.9-	0.94
Cypermethrin	10%EC	Biomethrin	1.74-	4.2	2.7(1.5-4.9)	14.1(8.2-	0.68
Lambdacyhalothrin	95% TG	Technical	1.56-	4.53	1.97(1.0-	12.9(6.6-	0.74
Orange oil	6%w/vSL	Prev-AM	1.8-	4.9	1.1(0.64-	5.4(3.2-9.1)	0.99

EC= Emulsifiable concentrate, TG=Technical grade, SL=Soluble liquid

Otherwise, treatment of pheromones or with parasitoid *Trichogramma evenecens* by [23], the biocide using bacteria or virus formulations revealed effective control carried out by [24]. About the diapause problems, [25] found that bioassay of *P. gossypiella* to lambda-cyhalothrin, chlorpyrifos, methomyl, emamectin benzoate and spinetoram), in laboratory showed susceptibility variation between the rosetted cotton flowers strain (more resistant) to methomyl and lambda-cyhalothrin than that of overwintering diapause strain. About resistance development toward those tested insecticides were discussed by [26], discovered strain resistant to profenofos of *P. gossypiella* (Saunders) collected at late season of 2013 from four Governorates in Egypt, where it was frequently used especially in Gharbia, and the lowest resistance values was in larvae of Kafrel-Sheikh. This because resistance development in this pest were takes a long time and needs many generations to develop. As a result of data means discovered by [27], high resistance ratio of *P. gossypiella* to spinosad during 20 successive generations was attained in F16 reached 62.5-fold, with no cross resistance between spinosad resistant strain and lambda-cyhalothrin or chlorpyrifos.

Enzymes assessments results

The data on the candidate enzymes activity measured in *P.gossypiella* after 24hrs exposed to OP, Py and oil sublethal concentration equal LC₅₀ data were in Table (2). Data shows that cypermethrin was recorded high value of *AChE* activity was 305 ($\mu\text{g AchBr}/\text{min}/\text{g.b.wt}$), followed by malathion was 268 then profenofos was 243. Nevertheless, orange oil recorded high value in *GST* activity monitoring was 161 ($\text{mmol sub.conjugated}/\text{min}/\text{g.b.wt}$), and recorded significant different from other the insecticide where cypermethrin was 95.3, malathion was 63 and profenophos was 53.3. Moreover, orange oil recorded the least value of alkaline phosphatase by 642.6 ($\text{mU}/\text{g.b.wt}$), alpha esterase was 512.7($\mu\text{g } \alpha\text{-naphthol}/\text{min}/\text{g.b.wt}$), and beta esterases activity was 458 ($\mu\text{g } \beta\text{-naphthol}/\text{min}/\text{g.b.wt}$), and the total protein 46.6 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{g body weight}$)

comparing with insecticides (Table 2). The highest values was cypermethrin in alkaline phosphatase, profenofos in alpha, beta esterase and the total protein. From this data concluded that all enzymes activity tested were not significantly higher than control and can be a related resistance mechanism in this pest population. Percentage of inhibition of Enzymes activity according to insecticide treatment data expressed as times compared with the control values were found in table (3). Where oil treatment recorded 3.3 times GST activity of control followed by cypermethrin recorded 2.76 times in alkaline phosphatase of control activity and 1.94 times of alpha esterase activity of control. In contrary the insecticides that showed decrease in activity was profenofos showed decreases in GST activity, malathion showed decrease in alpha esterase and the total protein in addition to orange oil showed decrease in alkaline phosphatase and the total protein. The in vitro enzyme inhibition is known to provide a useful tool for studying both the metabolism of xenobiotics such as catalyzes by GSTs and its involvement in resistance [6]. The activity reduction by a specific inhibitor may refer to one or more mechanisms that were involved. Generally, the developed resistance to any insecticide can cause variation in enzymes activities that studied by [26] estimated activity of *AChE*, alkaline, acid phosphatases, α & β nonspecific esterases and total protein contents as mechanisms for profenofos resistance in *P. gossypiella* field strains and proved significant positive correlation.

Table 2 . Enzyme activities of *P. gossypiella* larvae exposed to sub lethal treatment by Op, Py and orange oil insecticides.

Enzyme	Profenophos	Malathion	Cypermethrin	Lambdacyhalothrin	Orange	Control
Acetylcholinesterase	243.3±3.4	268±6.25	305±7.5	217.3±12.3	214.3±2.6	211.3±9.9
Glutathion S-	53.3±2.0	63±2.65	95.3±2.6	64.3±2.3	161±5	61±2.1
Alkaline phosphatse	2020±47.6	1476.6±25.9	2421±56	2078.3±29.5	642.6±30	1196.6±57.9
Alpha esterase	888±6.1	518.3±8.83	687.7±8.3	718.3±10.4	512.713.7	606.7±16
Beta esterase	678.3±15.2	535.5±17.7	663±11.9	577.3±9.0	458±2.9	476±15.0
Total protein	68.6±2.0	52.86±0.75	52.63±1.4	58.6±1.1	46.6±1.25	58.3±1.3

GSH= (mmolsub.conjugated/min/g.b.wt), AChE=(ug AchBr/min/g.b.wt), alkaline phosphatases = (mU/g.b.wt), alpha esterases = (ug α -naphthol/min/g.b.wt) and Beta esterase = (ug β -naphthol/min/g.b.wt).

The mode of action of any insecticide as a factor affecting enzyme activity and inhibition kinetic as found by [28], the 4th instar larvae of *S. littoralis* results revealed that Indoxacarb was the most inhibitive of α - esterase and GST activities, but Pyridalyl induced significant stimulation of β - esterase. About the effect of some oils used to control this pest on enzymes activities we found [29] studies on the newly hatched larvae treated with LC₅₀ for Jojoba oil, and flaxseed oil, and found noticed decreases in protein levels in *P.gossypiella* and increases in protein levels in *Earias insulana*. In addition, [27], found increases in *AChE* level and total protein in spinosad resistant strain compared with the susceptible, *P. gossypiella* and considered main mechanism of resistance to spinosad.

Table 3. Enzymes activities of *P. gossypiella* larvae sublethal treatment of Op, pyrethroid and one oil insecticides compared with the control.

Enzyme	Profenophos	Malathion	Cypermethrin	Lambdacyhalothrin	Orange oil
Acetalcholinesterase	1.15	1.26	1.31	1.03	1.29
Glutathion S-transferase	0.87	1.03	1.32	1.05	3.31
Alkaline phosphatse	1.68	1.23	2.76	1.73	0.86
Alpha esterase	1.46	0.85	1.94	1.18	1.39
Beta esterase	1.42	1.12	1.76	1.21	1.40

Total protein	1.17	0.90	1.17	1.01	0.93
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In other insects, we found [36], many insecticide compounds caused significant decrease in the total soluble protein content of the 4th instar larvae of *S. littoralis*. Like methomyl that caused increase in *AChE* and acid phosphatase activity and decrease in alkaline phosphatase but coumarin and azadirachtin increased α -esterase level. While others caused a decrease in β -esterase enzyme. As well as [30], found elevated levels of GST activity associated to insecticide resistance in many insects resistant to OPs in the housefly, *Musca domestica* and DDT in the fruit fly, *Drosophila melanogaster* [31] and pyrethroid resistant plant hopper, *Nilaparvata lugens* [32]. The scientist [33], concluded that whitefly resistant to insecticides exhibit high content of α - β -esterases and GST, while (*AChE*) is not a relevant mechanism in those populations. While [34], results of the 4th instar larvae of *S.littoralis* exposure indicated decrease in total proteins and alkaline phosphates in all insecticides except spinetoram. Nevertheless, teflubenzuron, spinetoram, hexaflumuron, and emamectin showed different detection levels in alpha and beta esterases and *AChE*, respectively.

Fig. 1. Enzymes activities of *P. gossypiella* larvae sub lethal treatment by *Op,Py* and one oil insecticides

Fig. 2. Enzymes activities of *P. gossypiella* larvae sub lethal treatment of Op, pyrethroid and one oil insecticides compared with the control

Histological slides demonstration results

The data of all histological changes picked up slides of *P. gossypiella* larvae after 24 hrs of OP, Py and orange oil insecticides LC₅₀ exposure were in figure (3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8), one replicate chosen and (magnification was H&E X 400). Each insecticide treatment and the control retain three body sliced slides as 3 replicates in the supplementary file. In general, 3 insecticide treatment (Malathion, profenfos and orange oil) briefly induced histological changes as degradation of basement membrane and peritrophic membrane, increases numbers of goblet cells, some cells loose its brush border and necrosis of most of columnar cells, lining epithelium midgut and disruption in longitudinal and circular muscles at high dose. In addition to hyperplasia of goblet cells at epithelial lifting and basement cells began to swell, vascular formation began to appear and accumulation of granular material in between muscle. Nevertheless, control slides showed no evidence of damage or cytoplasmic vacuolation. However, cypermethrin and lambdacyhalothrin considered most of insecticide affect cells compared with other insecticides remarkably shriveled cells, unidentified nuclei, and unclear granules correspondingly no evidence of goblet cell or regenerative cells also presence of numerous vacuoles destruction. These results proved that cypermethrin and lambdacyhalothrin was the most effective insecticide for killing this insect. Some similar histological observations after insect exposure to insecticides attained from literatures like, [35], the American cockroach *Periplaneta americana*, fed on deltamethrin. And [36] toxicity of methomyl and plant extracts (Coumarin and Azadirachtin) toxicity against larvae of *S. littoralis* (Boisd.). In addition to [37], the pyridalyl toxicity against *S. litura* larvae found hydropic degeneration, swollen mitochondria, elongation in endoplasmic reticulum and Golgi apparatus, shrunken nuclei and increase of unidentified clear granules appeared 6 hr after treatment. And [11] found spinosad toxicity against *P. gossypiella* in causing aberrations in the insect midgut layers. And the same with *Podisus nigrispinus* exposed to spinosad by [38].

Fig. 3. Histological changes of the cotton pink boll worm *P. gossypiella* larvae control sample mid gut showed the normal structure with the muscular layer followed internally by the intact thin basement membrane where the epithelium rested. The epithelial layer formed of one layer of columnar cells with dark round nucleus in the middle part of each cell, bearing an apical microvilli border. Also small goblet

cells are seen in great number between the columnar cells. and Lumen was surrounded by the peritrophic membrane which envelops the food.

Fig. 4. Histological changes of the cotton pink boll worm *P. gossypiella* larvae midgut exposed to sub lethal treatment of cypermethrin insecticide. The cross section showed completely separation or destruction of basement membrane cells, and Epithelial lining, detached in the midgut wall. and necrosis, desquamation in the lumen with lysis of the peritrophic membrane.

Fig. 5. Histological changes of the cotton pink bollworm *P. gossypiella* larvae treated by lambda-cyhalothrin sub lethal concentration. The cross section showed completely separation or destruction of basement membrane. Epithelial lining, the mid-gut wall detached or atrophied with necrosis of muscular layer and lysis in the peritrophic membrane.

Fig. 6. Histological changes of *P. gossypiella* larvae sub lethal treatment of malathion insecticides, cross section in the larvae mid-gut showed separation and detachment of basement and lysis of peritrophic membrane with sever vacuolar degeneration and necrosis in the epithelial lining the mid-gut.

Fig. 7. Histological changes of *P. gossypiella* larvae sub lethal treatment of profenofos insecticides, cross section in larvae mid-gut showed separation and detachment of basement and peritrophic membrane with sever vacuolar degeneration and necrosis in the epithelial lining the mid-gut.

Fig. 8. Histological changes of *P. gossypiella* larvae sub lethal treatment of orange oil, cross section in larvae mid-gut showed partial separation of basement membrane with mild vacuolar degeneration in the epithelial lining the mid-gut and necrosis of muscular layer.

The information about plant oil toxicity comprises data of [29], toxicity of Jojoba oil and flaxseed oil on neonate *S.littoralis* larvae achieved that vacuolization with hypertrophied lining mucosal epithelial, that blurred and Necrosis of nuclei. From *Cymbopogon citratus* essential oil and its main constituent citral was equal in toxicity against *S. littoralis*. Enzyme of Cytochrome P-450 and glutathione-S-transferase were inhibited, while carboxylesterases, α -esterase and β -esterase, were induced, these results found by [12]. Toxicity effect of Neem and flufenoxuron on other tissues as ovary and testis of red palm weevil *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus pupae* showed alterations of gonad structure, gamete productions through disruption of yolk granules accumulation and follicular epithelial cells, also degeneration and necrosis in germ cell lineage [39]. More symptoms were noticed in Chlorpyrifos and Cypermethrin toxicity in long-term exposure to the aquatic species *Paratelphusa jacquemontii* tissue exhibited epithelial lifting, edema, necrosis, hemorrhage, infiltration, lumen expansion and disappearance of haemocytes, atrophy, wavy appearance, fibers, fragmentation, loss of muscle structure, according to [40]. Also, dichlorvos toxicity on gill liver tissues *Cirrhinus mrigala* noticed by [41]. And dichlorvos toxicity on the gill liver tissue and tail muscle tissues *Duttaphrynus melanostictus* (Schneider) noticed by [42], was liver sinusoidal congestion and dilation, and changes in hepatocytes such as hyperchromatic nuclei and nuclear fragmentation, severe atrophy and myotomal disintegration, Hyperplasia, desquamation, and necrosis and epithelial lifting, oedema, lamellar fusion, collapsed and curly secondary lamellae.

The midgut histology of lepidopteran insects unexposed to insecticides is composed of the peritrophic membrane, mucosa, and musculature. The peritrophic membrane is chitinous forms and envelops the food particles, to protect the epithelium from mechanical damage and as a barrier against harmful chemicals and toxins [43]. The mucosa consists of midgut epithelium and regenerative cells embodied by groups closely packed, spherical nuclei with thin chromatin surrounded by a thin layer of clear cytoplasm. Columnar cells are epithelial cells have a brush border of microvilli in outside responsible for absorption and secretion of enzymes, goblet cells are ion homeostasis regulators, and the endocrine cells have endocrine function [44]. During insecticide toxicity some histological changes occur, as hypertrophy is the enlargement of an organ due to an increase in the size of cells. However, the increase in cell number was called 'Hyperplasia' [45]. The disturbance in the normal ionic balance of a cell, where sodium and water enter the cell named swelling tissue. The denaturation of intracellular proteins and enzymatic digestion of the lethally injured cell is being through formation of necrosis and cytoplasmic vacuolization and cell death [46]. Or DNA damage through oxidative toxicity on the reproductive organs [47, 48 and 49]. In addition to the factor of cell death studies by [50], and others investigate cell death mechanisms differences in Lepidoptera, other insects and *Drosophila melanogaster*, and the role of apoptosis and autophagy conferring to insecticide toxicity. The story where cells activate enzymes as key proteins that cleaved by cysteine protease, known as caspases, that degrade the cells own nuclear DNA and cytoplasmic proteins, and break up into fragments, called apoptotic bodies and contain portions of the cytoplasm and nucleus, then the dead cell and its fragments are rapidly gobbled [51]. An insect cell line tool developed to evaluate in vivo and in vitro toxic mechanisms of insecticide and effectiveness by [52].

CONCLUSION

The working with histological slides in line with toxicity studies or the enzymes change assessments were the most useful tool for study the insect pest biological transformation during toxicity of insecticides. In addition, the quantification of enzymes in insect bodies gives good information on the increase or decrease the proper enzyme during the toxicity of specific insecticide or toxic material.

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Hanan.: Quantification of enzymes and histology changes belongings to the pink boll worm *Pectinophora Gossypiella* (saunders) (lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) exposed to some insecticide toxicities

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